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Research Article

**STUDY TO KNOW THE COMMON PATHOGENS INVOLVED
IN DIABETIC FOOT INFECTION**¹ Dr Ahmad Walid, ² Dr Sayed Sultan Emad, ³ Dr Tanzeela Khan^{1,2} Al Nafees Medical College, Lahtrar Road Islamabad, ³ DHQ Teaching Hospital, Mirpur AJK.**Article Received:** March 2019**Accepted:** April 2019**Published:** May 2019**Abstract:****Objective:** To identify the most common pathogens in diabetic foot patients with different degrees of infection.**Study Design:** A descriptive study.**Place and duration of study:** In the Surgical Department Unit II of Holy Family Hospital, Rawalpindi for one year period from January 2018 to December 2018.**Patients and methods:** In this study, 120 diabetic patients with various types of foot infections due to causality and attended the surgical unit were included in the study. The patients included in this study were older than twelve years old and both sexes were present. A detailed history followed the Complete blood tests, clinical examination, renal parameters, complete urine test, CXR, X-ray foot, routine examinations for culture sensitivity and ECG were recorded. The lesions were classified according to the Wagner classification and appropriate surgical and medical management was given.**Results:** This analysis was performed in 120 diabetic patients; ninety-six (81.0%) were male and female were twenty-four (24%). The male to female ratio was 5:2. The majority of subjects (n = 66) were between 50 and 60 years of age. In most of these patients, the forefoot was mostly related to large or small fingers. Patients were divided into five classes according to the infection severity and Wegner's diabetic foot infection classification.**Conclusion:** Staphylococcus aureus, followed by pseudomonas aurogenosa and protein were the most common pathogen.**Key words:** Infection, Diabetic Foot Disease, Diabetic Foot Pathogens, Complication.**Corresponding author:****Dr. Ahmad Walid,**

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INTRODUCTION:

Diabetic patients are the most common and had serious problem of diabetic food. Gangrenous foot infections have been described as early as in 1000 A.D and diabetic foot infections are associated with significant mortality and morbidity. The lifetime risk of foot ulcers (type 1 or 2) may be as high as 25% for patients with diabetes. With the state of insulin therapy since the early 1900s, diabetes has now become a more common disease in the life expectancy of increased mortal and long-term complications of diabetic patients. Most patients are older, but more and more young patients acquired diabetic foot ulcers, and about 1/3rd of patients are below 51 years of age. In surgical treatment, diabetes mellitus most common complication is Diabetic foot. Prior to the advancement of effective antibiotics, the diabetic foot infection severity mostly requires amputation, independent of peripheral circulation. Foot amputations may be necessary, but most of them can be prevented by early diagnosis of complications and treatment. These infections combined with the incidence of a higher foot recovery resulted in a better understanding of the diabetic foot disease pathophysiology, more sophisticated diagnostic and vascular reconstruction method as well as the development of a better technique in wound care. The diabetic foot wounds microbiology varies depending on the degree of participation. According to the Maggit-Wenger classification Diabetic foot infection is classified. This study was carried out to determine the common pathogens of diabetic foot disease with a variable severity of infection.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

This descriptive study was held in the Surgical Department Unit II of Jinnah Hospital, Lahore for one year period from August 2017 to August 2018. One hundred twenty patients with long term diabetes mellitus and complications with different infection severity were selected for this analysis. Fifty-six (47.06%) patients were admitted because of a septic injury or gangrene in sixty-four (53.3%) patients. Data were obtained by a clinical examination and detailed history. The wound description or foot ulcer was observed. These subjects were evaluated for other systemic complications of diabetes mellitus and these types of problems were ruled out. In the examinations, whole blood test, blood glucose profile, complete urine test, kidney parameters, CXR, X-ray foot, blood glucose level and ECG were done. Tissue fragments from ulcers were sent for culture and sensitivity. The patients were classified and managed according to the Wegner classification by taking into account the severity of the infections at presentation the time. According to the degree of infection management was supposed. Data were collected and frequencies were met.

RESULTS:

In this analysis, 120 diabetes mellitus patients and foot infections were selected for the study. Of the patients, 96 (80%) were male and 24 (21%) were female. The male to female ratio was 5: 2. The large number of patients (n = 66) were between 50 and 60 years of age. The age distribution of these patients is shown in Table I.

Table No I: Age Distrubution (n=120)

AGE (IN YEARS)	QUANTITY	PERCENTAGE
<40	09	7.51%
40-50	34	28.30%
51-60	66	55.0%
ABOVE 60	11	9.10%

After physical examinations and examinations, these cases were divided into 5 classes according to the Maggit-Wegner classification shown in Table II.

Table No II: Maggit-Wegner classification of Diabetic foot ulcer

GRADE OF ULCER	CHARACTERISTICS
0	High risk foot with no ulceration
I	Skin involvement
II	Skin and soft tissue involvement
III	Skin, soft tissue and bone involvement
IV	Localized gangrene (forefoot, heel or toes)
V	Gangrene of entire foot

Staphylococcus aureus, 10 (8.3%) patients, and Proteus 8 (6.6%) patients, followed by pseudomonas in 79 patients (65.8%) was the most isolated organism from the wound, Table III.

Table No III: Organisms Cultured (n=120)

Infective Agent	Quantity	Percentage
Staphylococcus Aureus	79	65.8%
Pseudomonas Aeruginosa	10	8.30%
Proteus Vulgaris	08	6.60%
Others (Staphylococcus agalactae, Staphylococcus epidermidis)	23	19.10%

DISCUSSION:

Long-term diabetes mellitus leads to many multisystem complications. As reported in a US study, in 21-31% of patients foot ulcers were developed. One in 4 diabetic patients will develop a serious issue standing up throughout his life. Diabetic foot infections may develop as a result of ulcer, fracture or neuropathic or ischemic defects in the foot or nail skin (paronychia). However, in our population, the main problem is serious infection in diabetic foot patients. Key factors contributing to late presentation include walking barefoot, home interventions, trust in healers and inexperienced people, and undetected diabetes. Munawar J analysis proves that subjects who attained ulcers are: 1. Male and 4 females are more common in men, with a proportion of diabetic foot and 80% of our patients with 20% females. In another analysis study, 67.06% were male and female were 34.03%. In our analysis patients with superficial ulcers and redness were 21.6%, 10.8% had foot gangrene in 18.3% of the patients had 8.3%, gangrenous patches had pressure areas, 40.9% osteomyelitis, and poor granulation tissue deep ulceration. In a local study, general presentations were ulcers, 31% abscesses were 31%, and cordon was 12.5%. When patients with advanced disease reach the surgeon, these patients with grade three to five are predominant in our analysis. Depending on the degree of foot infection, the lesions are divided into 5 groups as in the Maggit-Wegner classification. For Grade one and two disease, broad-spectrum antibiotics such as clindamycin with amoxicillin and gentamicin plus clavulanic acid are usually given for minimum two to four weeks. However, metronidazole and ciprofloxacin have also been found useful. Superficial infections of the diabetic foot require local wound care, including removal of pressure on the ulcer, wound cleaning, and debridement of callus and necrotic tissue. In our

analysis, 22.06% of the patients were treated with antibiotic and fragmentation. In patients with superficial foot ulcers that did not improve for a long time with good results, 250 mg Fusidic Acid (Fucidin) was used twice daily. Patients with Grade III grade V disease required some form of amputation and had a large number of patients. In our study, 76.5% of the patients were in this class, unlike other local studies requiring amputation in only 36% of patients. In our study, 10.8% of the patients needed skin grafts. In our study, 9.1% of patients developed wound infection, 4% developed septicemia, and 1.6% used gas gangrene. In the industrialized world, the most common cause of non-traumatic lower extremity amputations are Diabetic foot complications. The lower extremity risk for amputation is 16 to 47 times higher in diabetics than normal subjects. In addition, the most common cause of admission in patients with diabetes are foot complications, as they account for 25% of diabetics in the US and Great Britain. In these patients, recurrent debridement and drainage of the abscess incision with hydrogen peroxide are frequently needed.

CONCLUSION:

Diabetic foot infection, the most serious problem of diabetic mellitus for surgeons, requires a proper management. Necessary investigations to assess the degree of infection during full and repeated examinations and presentations are very important. At some point, patients with only a small superficial ulcer have an underlying osteomyelitis of the foot bones. If a causal pathogen is detected, appropriate antimicrobial therapy can be initiated and better results can be obtained than empirical antibiotic therapy.

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